

Comparative analysis between Teachers' Education Goals and Social Change: An Exploratory Study of Nigerian University System

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Abstract

In Nigeria, despite clearly laid out policy goals with curriculum content mapped to its achievement, outcomes have continually fall short of expectations in terms of the kind of teachers envisioned in the policy document. The development of teachers with social change as a goal of teacher education remained a problem. This study aimed at describing teacher education goals for social change within Nigerian Teacher Education; and examining the relationship that exists between the Teacher Education goals and social change among the undergraduates. An exploratory sequential mixed method study was used to allow the leverage of the complimentary advantages of qualitative and quantitative methods for generating deeper insights into phenomena. In the first part, 11 lecturers from 11 universities were interviewed to generate qualitative data. In the second part, questionnaire was developed and administered to Teacher Education undergraduate. Participants in the quantitative study were 416 undergraduates at various levels of the Teacher Education programmes in the Nigerian public universities. The study assessed the factors of age, gender, subject area, and level/year of study as predictors of undergraduates' conceptualization of Teacher Education Goals (CTEG) for social change as well as CTEG as a predictor of social change. Thematic analysis and Structural Equation Model were employed to analyse the data collected for the study. The result showed that none of age, gender, year of study, and teaching subject significantly predicts CTEG. The study provided important information for policy, curriculum, strategy, and implementation in line with postmodern Teacher Education that is relevant for the twenty-first century.

Keyword: Teachers' education goals, social change, exploratory study, Nigerian Universities system

Introduction

The last two decades have brought rapid social, political, and economic changes which have transformed the structure of society in many countries around the world. The 21st Century society has been characterized by knowledge- driven economies, rapid information exchange and fast-moving communication technologies. Aside these social changes, there are a lot of challenges facing our communities, along with instant connectivity to a global society. The rapid social change has led to efforts in recent years towards educational reforms in European countries and other parts of the world. After the society

clearly and profoundly changed, it became necessary to reform education systems to be flexible, compatible with contemporary issues, and able to successfully tackle these challenges and the new realities. Meanwhile, studies affirmed that the success of any education depends on the quality of teachers, which in turn, depends on the effective teachings-learning process (Madhab, 2018; Mgaiwa, 2018). This suggests that would-be teachers need to be adequately equipped with knowledge and skills required for transforming the goals of teacher education into desired social change. In this context, teacher preparation programs in Nigeria are centrally and critically positioned in the national agenda (NPE, 2013), with a vision statement that Nigeria would like to: produce highly skilled, motivated, devoted, knowledgeable and creative teachers capable of raising a generation of Nigerian learners who can compete globally (FME, 2014). The National Policy on Education (FGN, 2013) also buttresses this by mandating Faculties of Education to produce highly motivated, conscientious, and creative classroom teachers that can promote creativity and adaptation to changes in the social life of the society.

While such a well-intentioned goal seems straightforward and clear, making it a reality has some challenges. The challenges begin with the conceptualization of teacher education goals among the teacher education undergraduates and the strategies employed to achieve the goals. This is because according to Ronnie (2016), simply stating a goal does not automatically benefit students, unless implemented correctly. This was supported by Pearson (2016) when it was held that though research in education has found goals setting to be essential for increasing student achievement and motivation, it is more important to get student buy-in regarding the value of assigned goals and make goal achievement personally meaningful for learners. Pearson goes further to state that clear goals provide explicit success criteria and evaluative standard that can be used to assess learners' progress. Moreover, measuring social change, according to Ebrahim (2019), begins with the organization's strategies and its theory of change. In line with these, the focus of this study is to examine the translation process of TE goals to social change within conceptualization of TE goals among TE undergraduates in Nigeria through the curriculum and instructional strategies.

The underpin theories for the study are goal setting theory by Locke and Latham (2006; 2017); and William E. Doll, Jr Four Rs curriculum theory of postmodern perspective on education (Qin, 2019). The goal setting theory was employed because of the theory's relevance to the conceptualization of teacher education goals. Then Doll's theory of change was also employed since we are in postmodern era (21st Century). Moreso, that Nigerian teacher education is having as its vision and goal, production of teachers with social change, who will be capable of coping with global trend in education. A postmodern approach to teacher education (TE) was therefore considered appropriate for effective professional socialization of the teachers as suggested by William E. Doll, Jr., in his curriculum theory of postmodern perspective on education (Qin, 2019). Prof. William E. Doll, Jr., the famous American postmodern curriculum theorist, offers us an effective curriculum/instruction strategy that can bring about appropriate translation of policy goals to required social change (Doll's, 1993; Qin, 2019). Doll posits that conceptualizing education within postmodernism means that education should foster, impact and result in social change. Doll's Pedagogical theory advocates the cultivation of students' comprehensive ability in the process of teaching; thus, it can bring positive effects to the transformation of the traditional perspectives on curriculum and instruction and help us solve the problems existing in the teacher education teaching and learning process (Doll's, 1993; Qin, 2019).

Despite Nigeria's clearly articulated policy goals for teacher education, which aim to produce highly skilled, motivated, and creative teachers capable of driving social change, the actual outcomes consistently fall short of these expectations. The gap between the envisioned goals and the actual performance of teacher education programs presents a significant challenge to the educational system. The fundamental issue lies in the conceptualization and implementation of teacher education goals. Many students enter teacher education programs accidentally, without genuine commitment to the profession, which undermines the potential for meaningful social transformation. The current approach to teacher education fails to effectively translate policy intentions into practical outcomes that can address the complex challenges of a rapidly changing 21st-century society. Moreover, there is a critical need to understand how teacher education programs can truly foster social change. The existing system struggles to develop teachers who are not just technically competent, but also socially conscious, adaptable, and capable of driving meaningful societal transformation. This requires a comprehensive examination of the goals, curriculum, and instructional strategies employed in teacher education programs. The research seeks to bridge this gap by investigating how undergraduate teacher education students conceptualize their educational goals and how these conceptualizations relate to potential for social change. By exploring the attitudinal, behavioral, and cognitive dimensions of teacher education goals, the study aims to provide insights that can help reshape teacher preparation to more effectively meet the demands of a dynamic and evolving educational landscape.

Objectives of the study

This study aimed at describing teacher education goals for social change within Nigerian Teacher Education; and examining the relationship that exists between the Teacher Education goals and social change among the undergraduates. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Determine the relationship between Teacher Education undergraduate students' conceptualization of Teacher Education goals and potential for social change.

Research Questions

The following research question was generated for this paper:

1. What is the association between Teacher Education undergraduate student's conceptualization of Teacher Education goals and social change?

Hypotheses

This study thus set out to test the following hypothesis:

1. The extent to which Teacher Education undergraduate student's conceptualize Teacher Education goals is significantly associated with social change.

Methodology

The research design used in this study was exploratory sequential mixed method. It is a research design where the researcher will collect qualitative data first and thereafter collect quantitative data for the same research study (Mihas, 2019). This study employed this research design because it was recommended for a study such as social change with unknown variables and absence of a guiding framework or theory (Creswell and Clark, 2018). The population for this study consisted of two groups: TE undergraduates in the Bachelor of Education programme in public universities in North-Central Nigeria and their lecturers. Nigeria consists of six (6) geopolitical zones with differing cultural, ethnic, geographical, and political structure. These factors have potentially strong implications for education and social change. A geopolitical zone thus represents the most homogenous socio-cultural entity within the multi-ethnic nation of over 250 million people. The North-Central geopolitical zone, also known as the Middle Belt, has an estimated population of around 29 million (14.51% of total population) spread across 6 states and the Federal Capital Territory (Ikoba, Jolayemi, & Sanni, 2018). The zone is located at the nation's centre and includes representative sections of other geopolitical zones and the federal capital territory (FCT) as well as a good presence of foreigners. These factors make the zone socially, culturally, and geopolitically neutral and representative of the nation as a whole. In addition, the researcher's deep knowledge of the social context, as well as teaching experience within the TE system in the north-central zone, comes in very readily, making this region an ideal context for this study which can be replicated in the future in other zones across the country.

Presentation of Results

RQ1: How is Teacher Education Goals for Social Change described within the context of Nigerian Undergraduate Teacher Education?

In attempt to obtain reliable and adequate data on TE Goals for Social Change in Nigeria, lecturers from target Universities in North Central Nigeria that are preparing the Undergraduate Teachers for the professional qualification were interviewed. The feedback from the interviews revealed that TE Goals for Social Change among the Undergraduate Teachers include attitudinal goals, behavioural goals, and cognitive goals. The attitudinal goal is described through four items including: (a) Commitment to teaching: Responses indicated that this concept is affected by societal and economic demands, dedication, the need to highlight the beauty of the profession. Lecturers submit that to promote attitudinal goals, only individuals who genuinely love the profession should be recruited for TE.

“There is lack of commitment on the part of our students because only few of them chose reading educational courses. The undergoing teacher education in this part of the world has no attraction or attention. *So, most of them are accidental teacher education students. Therefore, the level of commitment is low.*” [R2/M/42/11]

They noted unfortunately that TE is a tertiary option for most entrants into TE; their entry is mostly accidental and is due to the absence of ‘better’ options rather than a personal intention to be teachers. (b) Commitment to national goals: It is identified as a sign of commitment to teaching, and the lecturers believe service-learning opportunities stirs commitment:

“There are a lot they can do. Sending these graduates to the rural areas will do a lot of enhancing the beauty of these in formal and non- formal education. In the rural areas the rural teachers will not only work in the classroom after the class but also work in the farm... fishing, settling dispute and so on...” [R6/M/55/21].

(c) Fitness: Fitness was described as the ability to succeed in 21st century teaching and lecturers opined that to promote attitudinal goal, TE student recruitment should focus on best hands. They submit that non-formal education is more fit for producing high grade teachers than formal education and that social fitness is an indication of soundness, and it shown in effectiveness.

(d) Professionalism is shown in strong societal impact, and promoted through student orientation”:

“I have several of them that they are doing well, they are making waves in the teaching profession as many as I have seen that are motivated even those who never took us. Right now I have one of them who is a lecturer in the Kogi state university, he started with statistics then changed, when he came I motivated him and today he is a lecturer and even studying science subject inside sociology. I think they are making waves, those who listened to us and went through us.” [R3/F/59/23]

Behavioural goals are captured in conscientiousness and motivation. Lecturers believe that annual peer teaching can promote conscientiousness, and that objectivity and ethics are necessary qualities in undergraduate TE. In terms of motivation, they identified activeness in class, confidence, dynamism, engagement, and motivating TE students to appreciate themselves as critical factors.

“However, what we are able to achieve especially as with low-level students, I try to motivate them, integrate them into the profession, first of all, by given them their roles as teachers, that is why they are nation builders. I let them know that they are people who determine the impact of the future generation.” [R3/F/59/23].

Cognitive goals are captured in four concepts including creativity, efficiency, inquiry, and intellectual background. These concepts are described as follows in relation to undergraduate TE: (a) Creativity is shown in asking and answering technical questions, in assignment feedback and extra effort, in problem-solving, and in the use of interesting pedagogy and assessment. (b) Efficiency is shown in the demonstrate of knowledge ahead of teacher and class, ability to spot and correct teacher mistakes, communication and time management skills, including timeliness on assignment, classroom control, the use of demo and other edutech and resource utilization. They also noted that mandatory skill acquisition as graduation requirement can go a long way in promoting efficiency. (c) Inquiry is reflected in being ahead of class in content knowledge, contributing actively in class, eagerness to learn, inquiry and critical thinking, and inquisitiveness. (d) Intellectual Background will be promoted through a curriculum with room for more practical experience (TP and PT). It is shown in high CGPA or intellectual ability. It emphasizes 21t century pedagogy, methodology interaction and practice, continuous professional development, a robust TE Curriculum, and an effective foundation course.

Table 1: Testing the Research Hypotheses: Correlation among Variables

N = 416		Study_Yr	Age	CTEG
Study_Yr	Pearson Correlation	1	.263**	-.026
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.594
Age	Pearson Correlation	.263	1	-.109*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.027
CTEG	Pearson Correlation	-.026	-.109*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.594	.027	

*p < .05 **p < .01

1. There is a weak, positive correlation between year of study and age, which was statistically significant ($r = .263$, $n = 416$, $p = .000$). The standard graded programme of instruction where learners move to the next level of learning after every year will generally result in simultaneous increase in age and year of study, however, this progression is not automatic and only predicated on good performance. Respondents’ academic progression status was not assessed in this study. Hence, it cannot be determined whether this might have contributed to the weak correlation.
2. Age shows weak, negative correlations that are significant with both CTEG ($r = -.109$, $n = 416$, $p = .027$) and informal instruction ($r = -.112$, $n = 416$, $p = .022$).

Table 2: Parameter Estimates for Determining Independent Variables' Effect on Dependent Variable

Parameter	B	SE	95% CI	Wald χ^2	df	p	Exp(B)	95% CI for Exp(B)
Threshold: [SocChan = 1.00]	-10.806	0.782	[-12.339, -9.274]	191.067	1	< .001	0.000	[0.000, 0.000]

Parameter	B	SE	95% CI	Wald χ^2	df	p	Exp(B)	95% CI for Exp(B)
[SocChan = 2.00]	-7.883	0.734	[-9.322, -6.444]	115.241	1	< .001	0.000	[0.000, 0.002]
[SocChan = 3.00]	-4.194	0.653	[-5.473, -2.915]	41.299	1	< .001	0.015	[0.004, 0.054]
[SocChan = 4.00]	-1.019	0.612	[-2.219, 0.180]	2.775	1	.096	0.361	[0.109, 1.197]

Note. B = unstandardized coefficient; SE = standard error; CI = confidence interval; Exp(B) = odds ratio.

GENLIN parameter estimates for dichotomous variables (gender) and polytomous variables

H₀₂: Undergraduate teachers' gender does not significantly predict social change

H_{a2}: Undergraduate teachers' gender significantly predicts social change

The odds of male students scoring higher on the DV was 1.597, 95% CI [1.113, 2.293] times that of female students, and the effect is statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 6.449$, $p = .011$. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis, and accept the alternative hypothesis, and conclude that undergraduate teachers' gender significantly predicts social change.

H₀₃: Undergraduate teachers' teaching subject does not significantly predict social change.

H_{a3}: Undergraduate teachers' teaching subject significantly predicts social change.

The result shows that teaching subject has a statistically significant effect on the prediction of social change, Wald $\chi^2(1) = 6.490$, $p = .011$. The odds of students with teaching subject as language (including local and foreign languages) scoring higher on social change was 1.824, 95% CI [1.149, 2.896] times that of students with non-STEM teaching subjects, and the change is significant ($p < .05$). The odds of students with STEM teaching subject scoring higher on social change was 1.014, 95% CI [.678, 1.517] times that of students with non-STEM teaching subjects; the change is not significant ($p > .05$).

Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis that undergraduate teachers' teaching subject does not significantly predict social change, and we accept the alternative hypothesis, and conclude that some undergraduate teachers' teaching subject significantly predicts social change.

GENLIN parameter estimates for Ordinal and continuous IVs In terms of the ordinal (CTEG) and continuous IVs (age and year of study), we test the following pairs of hypotheses:

H₀₄: CTEG does not significantly predict social change among undergraduate teachers in Nigeria.

H_{a4}: CTEG significantly predicts social change among undergraduate teachers in Nigeria.

The result shows that CTEG has a statistically significant effect on the prediction of social change, Wald $\chi^2(1) = 324.350$, $p < .05$. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis, and accept the alternative hypothesis, and we conclude that level of CTEG significantly predicts social change among undergraduate teachers' in Nigeria.

H₀₅: Undergraduate teachers' age does not significantly predict social change

H_{a5}: Undergraduate teachers' age significantly predicts social change

The result shows that age shows $\chi^2(1) = .068$ and $p > .05$ which indicates that age does not have a statistically significant effect on social change. Hence, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that age does not statistically predict social change among undergraduate teachers.

H₀₆: Undergraduate teachers' year of study does not significantly predict social change

H_{a6}: Undergraduate teachers' year of study significantly predicts social change

For year of study ($\chi^2(1) = .097$; $p = .755$) do not have statistically significant effect on social change. In essence, TE students age and year of study do not predict social change, but their scores of CTEG does; that is, a TE student's level of conceptualization of TE goals has significant effect on social change.

Discussion of Findings

Description of TE goals for social change within Nigerian undergraduate TE focused on the evaluation of TE goals (as described in the Nigerian NPE document) as having social change as its focus. Within this context, social change was defined as significant changes in human interactions and societal norms with profound and longterm impact on cultural and social institutions (Mohammad, 2016; Denfey, 2017; Brown and Balts, 2017; Shah, 2017) where education could be both a factor for social change as well as the context for the significant changes brought about by social change. With change construed as a phenomenon involving a large number of persons engaging in activities that differ from those which they or their immediate forefathers engaged in some time before', within education, social change, in the simplest form can thus be conceived as modifications or changes in the values and social norms of community members, including learners, instructors, and other members as well as functioning of the community over time. The socialization of TE undergraduates – being the focused community in the context of this study – into the teaching profession, thus defines social change. With social change conceived as a process involving changes over time, for TE undergraduates, SC becomes the gradual, observable or measurable changes

towards the achievement of TE goals experienced over the course of the TE period. Following criticism of modernism, and the underlying philosophical assumptions (MBMS El-Baz, 2017), postmodernism, involving society-transforming changes that involves 'information advances...and the rise of a post-industrial order' (Vakhovskiy, L., Babichev, O., & Ivchenko, T. (2022)) became the lens for viewing education, and hence, teacher education in the twenty-first century. Thus, underpinned by the goal theory, the level of conceptualization of TE goals (CTEG) by TE undergraduates was identified as a factor that determines the achievement of social change as a focus of TE.

Individual learner factors have been studied extensively in terms of their moderating effects on learning. Vo, Seergobin and MacDonald (2018) examined the effect of age on reversal learning; they found that older adults learned more poorly than younger adults, thus suggesting a relationship between age and learning. In a similar study (Klein, Shner, Ginat-Frolich, Vervliet, & Shechner, 2020), the authors noted that adults exhibited a gradual decrease in differential danger ratings compared with younger learners. Both studies confirm age as predictive of learning. In their study of age-related cognitive decline, Vachon, Modchalingam and Hart (2020) identified similar ability among younger and older adults and argued that cognitive explanations for age-related decline in motor learning were limited.

This submission aligns with findings from this study. However, they also noted that training induced much larger shifts in older adults compared to younger adults. Thus suggesting that while age may not directly predict learning, it may predict shifts due to training (Griffin et al., 2017; Piotti et al., 2018; Vachon et al., 2020). Although this factor was not examined in this study, it may indicate an important focus of future research. Overall, a general difference between these studies and the current one is that the age range of learners in the current study is narrow, considering that age will generally be related to the level of study within formal education. Entry into the TE system requires individuals to have completed an initial 12 years of learning; hence, the entry point is relatively defined, and progression is predictable. In their study of gender effects in multimedia learning, Heo and Toomey (2020) showed that male participants consistently outperformed female participants in all learning tasks. Chung and Chang (2017) also suggested confirming a relationship between gender and learning. They studied the effect of gender on learning achievement and motivation, and showed that female learners' motivation is significantly higher than that of male learners. However, unlike Vachon et al (2020) who identified training as a moderating factor, they found game contents reduce the effect of gender.

Neither year of study nor teaching subject significantly predicted CTEG, but gender, teaching subject and the level of CTEG significantly predicted social change. Previous studies also reported divergent views on this. For example, Panadero, Fernandez-Ruiz and Sanchez (2020) reported significant effect of subject-matter on students on self-efficacy. Subject-matter knowledge has also been shown to be significantly related to teaching effectiveness (Manaf, Abdullah, & Osman, 2015). Yilmaz, Altinkurt, and Yildirim (2015) also showed that seniority or experience, subject matter and gender significantly affects teachers' level of organizational citizenship behaviors. They found that the level of seniority showed the strongest effect; female teachers exhibited much more citizenship behavior than male teachers. More senior teachers exhibited higher citizenship behaviours than less experienced teachers, and primary school teachers than subject matter teachers. It is hard to determine however, whether time spent practicing as teachers exerts effects that are different from the years spent as TE students.

Conclusion

The results of the study showed that attitudinal goals are described through commitment to teaching, commitment to national goals, fitness and professionalism. Behavioural goals are captured in conscientiousness and motivation. The result further showed that TE lecturers believe that peer teaching can promote conscientiousness, and that objectivity and ethics are necessary qualities in future teachers. They also identified activeness in class, confidence, dynamism, engagement, and inspiring TE students to appreciate themselves as critical factors for motivation. Cognitive goals are captured in four concepts including creativity, efficiency, inquiry, and intellectual background. These findings contribute to the basis for the development of the quantitative instrument for assessment of the level of social change among undergraduate TE students.

Recommendations

Based on this study finding, the following recommendations are made:

1. Educational institutions should reshape their teaching practices and curriculum to align with the desired social change in the field of education. This could lead to the development of a new generation of teachers who are more socially conscious, innovative, and equipped to address the evolving challenges in the society.

2. Educational institutions should adopt a holistic approach to teacher education, where both formal and informal aspects of the curriculum are considered. This would lead to a more comprehensive and effective learning experience for aspiring teachers.
3. This study took the data sample from public universities in the north-central region of Nigeria. Though the findings may be generalized for the region, further studies can explore other regions of the country. For example, the cultural difference can be explored to bring a variation in results.
4. This study was limited to undergraduate TE, implying teacher preparation within the university setting; future research into the other aspects of TE, including those that compare pre-tertiary and tertiary TE or tertiary TE and PD programme may shed light on important concepts.

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